

AUTHENTIC LEADERSHIP, PSYCHOLOGICAL EMPOWERMENT, AND ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT AMONG PRIVATE TERTIARY FACULTY: A CONVERGENT DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

This study utilized mixed methods particularly convergent mixed methods study to determine the significance of the influence of authentic leadership and psychological empowerment on organizational commitment of private tertiary faculty in Region XI. In this inquiry, an interview guide for the qualitative phase and adapted survey questionnaires in the quantitative phase were used. In addition, participants engaged in the qualitative phase through in-depth interviews, and in focus group discussion. The statistical tools utilized in quantitative data analysis were mean, standard deviation, one-way ANOVA, and independent t-tests. The status of authentic leadership and psychological empowerment was rated very high among private tertiary faculty. Further, the status of organizational commitment among private tertiary faculty was rated high. No significant differences were found in organizational commitment when analyzed by employment status, subject taught, school location, and type of school. However, a significant difference was found in organizational commitment when analyzed by length of service. The qualitative phase resulted to the three a priori themes: affective, continuance, and normative commitment. The grouping analysis revealed a significant

difference on the standpoints of private tertiary faculty on their organizational commitment based on the length of service. The nature of integration indicated the merging confirmation of quantitative and qualitative data. The study proposed an intervention program titled Strengthening Employee Retention and Loyalty: An Intervention Program to Enhance Continuance and Normative Commitment, which aims to enhance the continuance and normative commitment of private tertiary faculty.

Keywords: *Educational leadership, Organizational commitment, Private tertiary faculty, Convergent design, Region XI, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

Organizational commitment is a psychological state that describes an employee's engagement with an organization and impacts their decision to continue or end participation in the organization (Meyer & Allen, 1991). Furthermore, organizational commitment has received great attention because of its enormous impact on both personnel and the overall success of organizations (Bogler & Berkovich, 2022). However, the study of Tegegne (2024) revealed that teachers were observed to have low levels of organizational commitment. Also, the study conducted by Kassaw and Golga (2019) emphasized the limited availability of qualified and experienced instructors in universities as many teachers struggles on low commitment. Teachers usually show lower performance levels and contribute less to the institution's development.

Further, in Indonesia, teacher's low organizational commitment in the Merauke District has become a recurring concern for local educational policymakers. Low teacher attendance rates have been particularly observed, along with issues related to teachers' personality traits and professional skills (Werang et al., 2015). In Ethiopia, teachers had low levels of organizational commitment. Instructors with low organizational commitment are often characterized by frequent withdrawal behaviors and minimal engagement in collaborative or group activities (Tadesse, 2019). In Taiwan, only a moderate level of teachers' organizational commitment was observed emphasizing that schools should seek to strengthen teachers' organizational commitment (Lien & Lai, 2024). Likewise, teachers were observed to show reduced commitment to their organizations. They even showed decline participation and eagerness in their work (Malik, 2020; Akartuna & Serin, 2022). Even in Mexico, teachers only have a moderate extent of commitment to their institution (Perez et al., 2024).

Furthermore, in the Philippines, a study conducted by Aujero-Blanza (2019) specifically in Western Visayas revealed that the faculty have very low organizational commitment in general. Faculty are observed to have low emotional ties and cannot appreciate the benefits they can avail from the institution. In addition, Escal (2024) emphasized that the overall organizational commitment of faculty members was at a moderate level, whereas their continuance commitment appeared relatively low. Faculty members are less likely to stay at their current schools because they think leaving would be better for them. A significant number of them still think about leaving the company, even when they are offered better job opportunities.

Moreover, teachers' commitment to their organizations has been a constant issue in the Davao Region. Specifically, Parcia (2024) noted that teachers' heavy workloads and high expectations make them less committed to their jobs. Their dedication is further weakened by the absence of sufficient support from colleagues and school administrators. In addition, Guhao and Masunag (2024) emphasized that teachers with low organizational commitment frequently come late for work and abuse sick leave, which results in lost instructional time from ineffective substitute teachers or cancelled classes. Additionally, educators who exhibit a lack of organizational commitment frequently leave the teaching career or goes to another institution.

Consequently, Xu and Pang (2024) emphasized that authentic leadership fosters a stronger sense of commitment among teachers. Likewise, Khan and Jamil (2023) accentuated that teachers' organizational commitment is influenced by authentic leadership. When leaders demonstrate authentic leadership practices, this encourage teachers to be more committed to the institution. Similarly, the study of Rego et al. (2016) demonstrated that authentic leadership has a significant impact on organizational commitment. Authentic leadership significantly influences the normative aspect of commitment, suggesting that educators are likely to experience a profound feeling of obligation to remain within the institution under the guidance of authentic leaders.

In addition, organizational commitment of teacher will increase when teachers have high psychological empowerment (Ibrahim, 2020). Also, empowerment and organizational commitment among educators at Malaysian universities were favorably connected. When perception of work empowerment increases, employees' organizational commitment will gradually rise also (Muda & Fook, 2020). Likewise, psychological empowerment influences various behavioral outcomes, including organizational commitment. Thus, it is crucial to establish an environment that promotes psychological empowerment among employees in order to have a harmonious workplace (Aggarwal et al., 2018). Added to that, the inquiry by Bin Jomah (2017) noted that psychological empowerment correlates with organizational commitment indicating a profound positive relationship. It specifies that as psychological empowerment increases, organizational commitment also increases. Psychological empowerment, focused on employees' experiences and responsibilities, significantly enhances commitment in institutions, validating its role in strengthening organizational dedication.

Despite a substantial body of research on authentic leadership, psychological empowerment, and organizational commitment, noteworthy gaps remain in terms of methodology and context. Most existing studies have adopted either survey (Yao & Ma, 2024) or interview methods (Gürbüz et al., 2023), and tend to focus on single-variable relationships. Also, prior research has largely focused on public school teachers (Menesis, 2024). The researcher failed to come across any existing studies that explore these variables within private tertiary educational institutions, particularly in the local context. To address these gaps and to establish the novelty of this study, a more integrative approach was adopted by examining the three variables specifically the authentic leadership, psychological empowerment and organizational commitment

among private tertiary faculty in Region XI, utilizing a convergent design.

This study enhanced the social value of education by highlighting the significance of authentic leadership and psychological empowerment in cultivating organizational commitment among faculty members in private tertiary institutions. The results can help school leaders make workplaces that are more helpful and motivating.

This study was aligned with significant Sustainable Development Goals, specifically SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth) because the results speak volumes about fostering a productive, motivated, and committed workforce through effective leadership and empowerment, which ultimately enhances institutional performance and contributes to sustainable economic growth. It also fits with SDG 4 (Quality Education) because it emphasizes the need for teachers to develop their leadership skills and encourage their professional growth, which will improve the quality of instruction and the overall learning environment. It also supports SDG 16 (Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions) because it stresses the importance of shared leadership, ethical behavior, and psychological empowerment in creating open, welcoming, and accountable academic institutions that uphold integrity and justice in the way they run their organizations.

There will be many ways to distribute the study's results so that they reach the proper audience. The research will be shared with other academics by being presented at an international research conference. The results will also be shared with private colleges and universities through conferences, seminars, or webinars for administrators and teachers that focus on practical ways to encourage real leadership, psychological empowerment, and devotion to the organization. Finally, the goal will be to get published in peer-reviewed publications.

Research Questions

1. What is the status of authentic leadership, psychological empowerment and the organizational commitment of private tertiary faculty?
2. Is there a significant difference in organizational commitment among private tertiary faculty when analyzed by employment status, subject area taught, school location, type of school, and length of service?
3. What are the standpoints of private tertiary faculty on their organizational commitment?
4. How do the groupings analysis define the experiences of private tertiary faculty regarding their organizational commitment?
5. What results emerge from comparing the quantitative data with the qualitative results on the organizational commitment among private tertiary faculty?
6. What intervention scheme can be crafted from the results of the study?

METHODOLOGY

This research was conducted in Region XI, known as the Davao Region, which is an administrative region situated in the southeastern part of Mindanao, Philippines. This research employed a mixed methods approach, explicitly utilizing a convergent design. Mixed methods research is an approach that involves the collection, analysis, and integration of quantitative and qualitative data to draw conclusions that leverage the strengths of each data type (Creswell, 2021; Creswell & Clark, 2017). Moreover, convergent design encompasses the concurrent collection and analysis of quantitative and qualitative data within a similar time frame, facilitating a comparative analysis of the data (Moseholm & Fetters, 2017). Also, a descriptive-comparative method involves the gathering of data to answer queries on the present status of the variables and compares two or more groups on a specific variable. This approach does not involve variable manipulation but focuses on naturally occurring differences, making it suitable for educational and social research where ethical or practical constraints limit experimental control (Calderon & Gonzales, 2018). Meanwhile, qualitative research design serves as a way for discovering and understanding the meanings that people give to social or human issues (Creswell, 2014). The goal of qualitative research is to comprehend how individuals construct their worlds, interpret their experiences, and assign meaning to them (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016). Additionally, phenomenology was employed to scrutinize the qualitative characteristics of the research's variables during qualitative phase. Additionally, Neubauer et al. (2019) define phenomenology as a methodology in research aimed at elucidating the essence of a phenomenon through the perspectives of individuals who encountered it. The aim of phenomenology is to explicate the significance of this experience, encircling both the content of the experience and manner in which it was perceived.

In the quantitative phase, the study involved 313 full-time faculty members from selected private tertiary institutions in Region XI. The sample size of 313 respondents was determined using the Raosoft Sample Size Calculator. Stratified random sampling was used to guarantee representation across key subgroups such as school population and employment status such as permanent vs. part time. Random sampling within each stratum was conducted using a list provided by the institutions' HR departments to ensure unbiased representation.

In the qualitative strand, purposive sampling was employed to deliberately select 17 participants from among those who completed the survey and voluntarily indicated their willingness to participate in further discussions. This non-probability sampling technique allows the researchers to identify individuals who can provide rich, in-depth insights based on specific characteristics related to the inquiry. Also, Etikan et al. (2016) highlighted that purposive sampling is a method where participants are chosen based on the researcher's assessment of which individuals will be most beneficial or representative.

In the quantitative phase, adapted questionnaires were used to obtain responses from the respondents regarding the variables examined in this study. These

questionnaires include The Authentic Leadership Questionnaire developed by Walumbwa et al. (2008) which consists of four dimensions: self-awareness, relational transparency, internalized moral perspective, and balance processing; The psychological empowerment tool was adapted from Spreitzer (1995) which has four dimensions: meaning, competence, self-determination, and impact, and the questionnaire on Organizational Commitment was adapted from Allen and Meyer (1990) which consists of three dimensions: affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative Commitment. These researchers used these questionnaires to achieve the main aim of this study which was assessing the influence of authentic leadership and psychological empowerment on organizational commitment of private tertiary faculty.

The first part of the questionnaire was to determine the status of authentic leadership, the second part was to determine the status of psychological empowerment, and the third part was to determine the status of organizational commitment of private tertiary faculty. Experts evaluated the questionnaires to ensure content validity. Their feedback and suggestions were combined into the final version of the research instrument to guarantee accurate measurement and alignment with the study's objectives. Also, a pilot test was conducted to evaluate the internal consistency of the research instrument, revealing acceptable reliability coefficients ranging from 0.898 to 0.969.

Authentic Leadership Questionnaire. The questionnaire has a reliability coefficient of 0.75, as measured by Cronbach's alpha. The estimated internal consistency alphas for each dimension were also at acceptable levels: self-awareness (0.79), relational transparency (0.72), internalized moral perspective (0.73), and balanced processing (0.76). The study of Xu and Pang (2024) also reported a Cronbach alpha of 0.968, indicating good reliability. Further, the pilot test conducted in this study indicated a Cronbach alpha of 0.969 of authentic leadership.

This scale consists of three indicators, namely: self-awareness composed of 4-items, rational transparency that is composed of 5-items, internalized moral perspective with 3-items, and balanced processing that has 4-items. The tool is a 16-item construct from 5-Strongly Agree to 1- Strongly Disagree. The ratings are described as follows:

Mean Range	Description	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very High	The authentic leadership is always manifested.
3.40-4.19	High	The authentic leadership is oftentimes manifested.
2.60-3.49	Moderate	The authentic leadership is sometimes manifested.
1.80-2.59	Low	The authentic leadership is rarely manifested.
1.00-1.79	Very Low	The authentic leadership is never manifested.

Psychological Empowerment Questionnaire. It consists four indicators: Meaning, Competence, Self-determination, & Impact. Each indicator is composed of 3 items. The reported Cronbach's alpha values are as follows: Meaning (0.85), Competence (0.84), Self-determination (0.80), and Impact (0.85). In addition, Hartmann (2003) also conveyed that the reliability coefficient of this tool is 0.79 using Cronbach's alpha. Meanwhile, pilot test conducted in this study indicated a.898 Cronbach alpha of psychological empowerment.

The tool is a 12-item construct from 5-Strongly Agree to 1- Strongly disagree. The ratings are described as follows:

Mean Range	Description	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very High	Psychological empowerment is always observed.
3.40-4.19	High	Psychological empowerment is oftentimes observed.
2.60-3.49	Moderate	Psychological empowerment is sometimes observed.
1.80-2.59	Low	Psychological empowerment is seldom observed.
1.00-1.79	Very Low	Psychological empowerment is not observed.

Organizational Commitment Questionnaire. This has three indicators namely: Affective Commitment which has 8 items, Continuance Commitment composed also of 8 items and Normative Commitment has also 8 items. The tool is a 24-item construct from 5-Strongly Agree to 1- Strongly Disagree. The Cronbach alpha for affective commitment is 0.87, for continuation commitment is 0.75, and for normative commitment is 0.79. Further, the pilot test conducted in this study obtained a 0.945 Cronbach alpha of organizational commitment.

Mean Range	Description	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very High	Organizational commitment is always evident in the workplace.
3.40-4.19	High	Organizational commitment is oftentimes evident in the workplace.
2.60-3.49	Moderate	Organizational commitment is sometimes evident in the workplace.
1.80-2.59	Low	Organizational commitment is rarely evident in the workplace.

1.00-1.79

Very Low

Organizational commitment is never evident in the workplace.

An interview guide was used in the qualitative component for data collection from participants. The interview guide questions were validated by field experts for IDI and FGD. This included both guiding and probing questions. The interview guide consists of three sections: a letter of permission for participants, Part I, which contains preliminary information, and Part II, which encompasses the actual interview.

Experts were consulted to address issues of validity with the study's methods. The utilization as well as implementation of convergent design were discussed with the help of an expert. The experts checked and validated the adopted and revised survey questionnaires as well as the interview guide questions. The reliability coefficient of the questionnaires was provided depending on the Cronbach alpha or alpha coefficient specified in the study where they anchored. Stratified random sampling was utilized for selecting participants in the survey. This ensured that all relevant subgroups are represented proportionally in my sample. Also, purposive sampling was utilized to choose participants for one-on-one interviews and focus group discussion. For the qualitative data, a duplicate of the transcriptions was sent to the relevant private tertiary faculty participant to ensure that nothing is changed in the transcript. Expert statisticians were consulted for quantitative data, particularly in terms of statistical analysis. To ensure the authenticity of this study, all expert ideas were accepted with the adviser's approval. The data from the survey questionnaire were examined in the quantitative section of this inquiry.

The following statistical procedures were utilized in order to examine the numerical data that was gathered from the private tertiary faculty through the use of survey questionnaires: the mean, the standard deviation, the independent t-test, and the analysis of variance (ANOVA). The standard deviation was used to measure the dispersion of the data in relation to its mean, while the mean was used to evaluate the status of authentic leadership, psychological empowerment, and organizational commitment among private tertiary faculty. Both of these metrics were utilized in the evaluation process. Specifically, these instruments were utilized in order to answer the first research question. The t-test was employed to assess the statistical differences between the means of two groups, specifically for private tertiary faculty's employment status, subject taught, school location, and kind of institution. The ANOVA was employed to assess the statistical differences among the means of many groups, specifically to determine if private tertiary faculty vary in length of service. These instruments specifically aided the researcher in addressing Research Question 2.

The process of thematic analysis involves examining data in order to identify recurring topics, concepts, and patterns. In order to become familiar with the data, the researcher performed a thorough examination of the transcripts on many occasions while conducting the theme analysis. For the purpose of producing preliminary codes, the data were structured. Following the reduction of the codes into more manageable

units of meaning, the codes were subsequently evaluated and grouped according to trends. After being established, analyzed, adjusted, and refined, the themes were discussed. Following that, the researchers conducted an analysis to determine the themes' degree of coherence and distinctiveness.

Following the completion of the analysis, the researcher integrated and compared the results from both phases in order to identify areas of convergence, divergence, or complementarity. The integration of these two types of data allowed for a more comprehensive knowledge of the phenomenon than could be obtained via the use of quantitative or qualitative data for themselves.

RESULTS

Status of Authentic Leadership

Presented in Table 1 the status of Authentic Leadership among private tertiary faculty in Region XI. Computations yielded an overall mean of 4.45 described as very high which means that the authentic leadership among private tertiary faculty in Region XI is always manifested. In addition, the overall standard deviation is .59 which is less than 1 which is an indicator of small range of dispersion.

Table 1
Status of Authentic Leadership

	Mean	SD	Description
Relational Transparency	4.48	.57	Very High
Internalized Moral Perspective	4.42	.58	Very High
Balanced Processing	4.42	.58	Very High
Self-Awareness	4.38	.62	Very High
OVERALL	4.45	.59	Very High

Status of Psychological Empowerment

Presented in Table 2 is the status of psychological empowerment of private tertiary faculty in Region XI. This variable was measured in terms of meaning, competence, self-determination, and impact. The computations yielded an overall mean of 4.48, described as very high which means that psychological empowerment is always observed. More so, the overall standard deviation is .54, indicating a minimum range of dispersion on respondents' responses.

Table 2
Status of Psychological Empowerment

	Mean	SD	Description
Meaning	4.69	.50	Very High
Competence	4.46	.59	Very High
Self-determination	4.44	.61	Very High
Impact	4.27	.70	Very High
OVERALL	4.48	.54	Very High

Status of Organizational Commitment

Presented in Table 3 is the status of Organizational Commitment of private tertiary faculty in Region XI. This variable was measured in terms of affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment. Computations yielded an overall mean of 4.10 described as high which means that organizational commitment among private tertiary faculty is oftentimes evident in the workplace. Moreover, The overall standard deviation is .44, which is less than 1, indicating a minimal range of dispersion.

Table 3
Status of Organizational Commitment

	Mean	SD	Description
Affective Commitment	4.35	.60	Very High
Continuance Commitment	4.00	.00	High
Normative Commitment	4.01	.65	High
OVERALL	4.10	.44	High

Significance of the Difference of the Organizational Commitment among Private Tertiary Faculty in Region XI when Analyzed by Employment Status

Displayed in Table 4 the result which purpose is to determine the significant difference in organizational commitment when analyzed by employment status. The results yielded a t-value of 1.313 and a p-value of 0.62 which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. This specifies that there is no significant difference on the organizational commitment of private tertiary faculty in Region XI when analyzed by employment status.

Table 4
Significance of the Difference of the Organizational Commitment among Private Tertiary Faculty in Region XI when Analyzed by Employment Status

Employment Status	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	p-value	Remarks
Full Time	4.12	.51	1.312	.062	Not Significant
Part-Time	4.06	.32			

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Significance of the Difference of the Organizational Commitment among Private Tertiary Faculty in Region XI when Analyzed by Subject Taught

Presented in Table 5 the result of testing the significant difference in the level of organizational commitment of private tertiary faculty in Region XI. As shown in the table, the overall t-value is -.132 with a computed p-value of 0.895. This suggests that the difference in organizational commitment between the groups is extremely minimal and not statistically significant.

Table 5
Significance of the Difference of the Organizational Commitment among Private Tertiary Faculty in Region XI when Analyzed by Subject Taught

Subject Taught	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	p-value	Remarks
General Education Subjects	4.09	.37	-.132	.895	Not Significant
Professional Courses/Subject	4.10	.52			

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Significance of the Difference of the Organizational Commitment among Private Tertiary Faculty in Region XI when Analyzed by School Location

The results of testing the significance of the difference in the level of organizational commitment among private tertiary teachers in Region XI when analyzed according to school location are reflected in Table 6. As shown in the table, the overall t-value is, with a computed p-value greater than 0.05, indicating that the difference between school location is not statistically significant.

Table 6
Significance of the Difference of the Organizational Commitment among Private Tertiary Faculty in Region XI when Analyzed by School Location

School Location	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	p-value	Remarks
urban	4.10	.44	-.105	.917	Not Significant
rural	4.11	.33			

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Significance of the Difference of the Organizational Commitment among Private Tertiary Faculty in Region XI when Analyzed by School Type

Presented in Table 7 the result of testing the significance of the difference in the level of organizational commitment among private tertiary faculty in Region XI according to school type. As shown in the table. The overall t-value is with a computed p-value greater than 0.05, indicating that the difference between school types is minimal and not statistically significant.

Table 7
Significance of the Difference of the Organizational Commitment among Private Tertiary Faculty in Region XI when Analyzed by School Type

Type of School	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	p-value	Remarks
sectarian	4.07	.40	-.925	.356	Not Significant
non-sectarian	4.12	.48			

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Significance of the Difference of the Organizational Commitment among Private Tertiary Faculty in Region XI when Analyzed by Length of Service

Shown in Table 8 is the result of testing the significance of the difference in the level of organizational commitment of teachers in private tertiary faculty in Region XI when analyzed according to length of service. As shown in the table, the overall F-value is 3.077 ($p < 0.05$), which suggests that the variation between sample is high enough relative to the variation within the samples. Therefore, there is significant difference in the level of organizational commitment of private tertiary faculty in Region XI when analyzed according to length of service.

Table 8
Significance of the Difference of the Organizational Commitment among Private Tertiary Faculty in Region XI when Analyzed by Length of Service

Length of Service	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	F	p-value	Remarks
below 5 years	4.02	.40	.034	3.077	.017	Significant
6-10 years	4.09	.35	.040			
11-15 years	4.20	.48	.062			
16-20 years	4.20	.67	.175			
above 20 years	4.31	.60	.151			
Total	4.10	.44	.025			

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Profile of the Participants in the Qualitative Phase

Displayed in Table 9 the profiles of the participants engaged in the qualitative phase, specifically during the in-depth interviews (IDI) and focus group discussions (FGD). There were ten participants in the in-depth interviews and a total of seven participants in the focus group discussion

Table 9
Profile of Participants for the Qualitative Phase

Code	Employment Status	Subject Taught	School location	School type	Length of Service (Year)
FGD_01	Full-Time	General Education	Urban	Nonsectarian	6-10
FGD_02	Full-Time	Professional Subject	Urban	Nonsectarian	11-15
FGD_03	Full-Time	General Education	Urban	Sectarian	6-10
FGD_04	Full-Time	Professional Subject	Urban	Nonsectarian	16-20
FGD_05	Part-time	General Education	Urban	Sectarian	6-10
FGD_06	Part-time	Professional Subject	Rural	Nonsectarian	Below 5
FGD_07	Part-time	General Education	Rural	Sectarian	11-15
IDI_01	Part-time	General Education	Urban	Sectarian	Below 5
IDI_02	Full-Time	Professional Subject	Urban	Sectarian	6-10
IDI_03	Part-time	General Education	Urban	Sectarian	Below 5
IDI_04	Full-Time	Professional Subject	Rural	Sectarian	10-15
IDI_05	Full-Time	General Education	Urban	Nonsectarian	Below 5
IDI_06	Full-Time	General Education	Urban	Nonsectarian	15-20
IDI_07	Full-Time	General Education	Rural	Nonsectarian	Below 5
IDI_08	Full-Time	Professional Subject	Urban	Sectarian	6-10
IDI_09	Full-Time	General Education	Urban	Sectarian	11-15
IDI_10	Full-Time	Professional Subject	Urban	Nonsectarian	21 and above

Standpoints Of Private Tertiary Faculty in Region XI on Their Organizational Commitment: A Priori Themes

Presented in Table 10 are the essential themes and core ideas about standpoints of private tertiary faculty in Region XI on their organizational commitment. After analyzing the data gathered from the responses of the participants, the following three essential themes emerged from the answers of the two study groups: affective commitment, continuance commitment, normative commitment.

Table 10
Standpoints Of Private Tertiary Faculty on Their Organizational Commitment

Essential Themes <i>(a priori)</i>	Core Ideas
Affective Commitment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Receiving recognition and trust from leadership • Appreciating student success and gratitude • Supporting professional growth opportunities • Finding purpose in teaching as vocation • Experiencing positive institutional culture • Valuing small gestures of appreciation
Continuance Commitment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relying on financial incentives and compensation • Accumulating tenure and institutional experience • Pursuing career advancement opportunities • Avoiding loss of benefits and institutional support • Benefiting from scholarship and study opportunities • Fulfilling breadwinner responsibility
Normative Commitment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aligning with institutional mission and values • Showing gratitude for institutional opportunities • Fulfilling obligation to students' success • Upholding collegial responsibility • Observing cultural expectation of loyalty • Mirroring leadership's example of commitment

Joint Display of Quantitative and Qualitative Results

The two datasets in this study were compared using a combined presentation. The combined quantitative and qualitative results are shown in Table 11, which offers a concise and well-structured side-by-side comparison of the two datasets.

Table 11
Joint Display of Quantitative and Qualitative Results

Research Area	Quantitative Results	Qualitative Results	Nature of integration
Status of organizational commitment	<p>The respondents rated all three indicators of organizational commitment with an overall high mean score of 4.10, indicating that the respondents are oftentimes committed to their organization.</p> <p>One indicator, affective commitment (4.35), was rated very high by the respondents, while the rest were rated high, ranging from 4.00 to 4.10</p> <p>Refer to Table 3</p>	<p>All the three indicators (a priori) in Table 10 emerged in the qualitative phase: Affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment. The interview results confirmed the overall high mean score of organizational commitment in Table 3</p> <p>The indicator on affective commitment was exhibited by most of the participants towards their organization as gathered from them during the interview. The interview result coincides with the quantitative result where one theme (a priori) obtained very high mean scores. Receiving recognition and trust from leadership was also claimed by the participants as being practiced by organization.</p> <p>Refer to Table 10</p>	<p>Merging-confirmation</p> <p>Merging-confirmation</p>
Significance of the Difference of the overall Organizational commitment in	<p>There is no significant difference in the overall organizational</p>	<p>The overall organizational commitment was analyzed in terms of</p>	<p>Merging-confirmation</p>

<p>terms of employment status, subject area taught, school location, type of school, and length of service</p>	<p>commitment in terms of employment status (t=1.312, p>.05); subject area taught (t=-.132, p>.05); school location (t=-.105, p>.05); type of school (t=-.925, p>.05)</p> <p>There is one significant difference when some indicators of Organizational commitment were analyzed singularly:</p> <p>OC by length of service (F= 3.077, p<.05)</p>	<p>employment status, subject area taught, school location, type of school, showed no significant difference when the participants were interviewed confirming the quantitative results in Tables 4-7</p> <p>In terms of length of service, the analysis of the interview disclosed that some of those who stayed within a certain year, has developed commitment.</p> <p>This suggests that employees' commitment levels vary depending on how long they have been with the institution.</p>	<p>Merging-confirmation</p>
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Intervention Scheme

The following table presents the **Intervention Scheme for Strengthening Continuance and Normative Commitment**. The areas of concern were drawn from the survey results, specifically the two lowest mean indicators. These represent the weakest aspects of employees' commitment and serve as the foundation for designing targeted interventions.

Table 12
Proposed Intervention Scheme
Strengthening Employee Retention and Loyalty: An Intervention Program to Enhance Continuance and Normative Commitment

Areas of Concern	Objectives	Strategies/ Activities	Output	Person/ Office Responsible	Timeline
Continuance Commitment	To broaden employees' awareness of	- Conduct career development	Increased perception of available	HR Department Faculty	Semi-annual

	career development opportunities within the organization	and succession planning workshops - Provide transparent information on internal promotion paths and professional growth opportunities	career pathways within the organization	Development Committee	workshops (2x a year)
Continuance Commitment	To strengthen employees' sense of security by highlighting unique institutional benefits	- Benchmark and improve compensation/benefits package - Communicate institutional advantages (scholarships, grants, research opportunities, mission-driven culture)	Stronger recognition of school's unique benefits compared to other organizations	HR Department Finance Office University President's Office	Annual compensation review
Normative Commitment	To reinforce loyalty and ethical responsibility in employment	- Conduct values formation and loyalty seminars - Share testimonies of long-serving employees - Integrate organizational values in professional development sessions	Enhanced moral perspective on loyalty and long-term service	Office of Student Affairs Mission & Identity Office HR Department	Annual values seminar
Normative Commitment	To cultivate moral obligation and gratitude for	- Launch recognition programs for service milestones	Heightened sense of gratitude, belonging, and moral	HR Department University Administration	Ongoing mentorship (year-round) Annual

	opportunities provided by the organization	- Strengthen mentorship between senior and junior employees - Organize community outreach with institutional branding	obligation to remain	Community Extension Office	recognition program
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DISCUSSION

Status of Authentic Leadership among Private Tertiary Faculty

The status of authentic leadership of supervisor in Region XI was found to be descriptively very high. This means that the authentic leadership among private tertiary faculty is always manifested. This implies that supervisors consistently demonstrate transparency, ethics, balanced judgement, and self-awareness, fostering trust, openness, and integrity. This means they openly communicate, admit mistakes, align action with core values, consider different perspectives and remain conscious of how their behavior affects others. This creates an empowering environment where members feel valued, strengthens relationships, and promotes a positive culture.

This result supports the study of Roncesvalles and Gaerlan (2021) which reported a high level of authentic leadership as supervisors exhibit caution when making decisions by having a strong code of conduct and asking their subordinates for input and different points of view. Moreover, the study verified the study of Başaran and Kiral (2020) on the authentic leadership of supervisors in which they found a high level of authentic leadership in all its dimension.

Authentic leadership is defined by positivity and transparency, cultivating a supportive organizational environment. This leadership style aligns closely with the principles of positive leadership and promotes employee innovation and commitment (Liu et al., 2025). Consequently, school administrators as perceived by teachers exhibit a moderate level of authentic leadership behaviors. Teachers frequently believe that their school administrators do not go far enough in displaying these kinds of behaviors, according to a modest level of perspective. Such behaviors as being open, honest, and sincere with other school employees; having an internalized moral perspective; balance-processing information before making decisions; and being mindful of their own strengths and weaknesses are not displayed by school administrators at a high enough level (Okçu & Admis, 2022; Srivastava & Dhar, 2017).

Status of Psychological Empowerment Among Private Tertiary Faculty

The level of psychological empowerment of private tertiary faculty in Region XI was found to be very high. This means that the psychological empowerment of private tertiary faculty is always observed. This implies that they manifested a strong sense of meaning in their work, recognizing its importance and personal significance. Their high competence reflects confidence in their skills and abilities, enabling them to perform their responsibilities excellently. Likewise, their self-determination demonstrates autonomy and independence in deciding how to accomplish their work. Also, their strong sense of impact highlights their belief that they can influence outcomes in their departments, contributing to organizational growth and improvement.

This finding echoes the study of Crispo (2025) whose study revealed a very high level of psychological empowerment of educators. Empowered educators demonstrate a solid sense of competence and autonomy, permitting them to execute their teaching responsibilities with confidence and independence. They are motivated to participate in continuous professional development, which further strengthens their self-efficacy and effectiveness in the classroom. Such educators view their work as meaningful, have confidence on their capability to reinforce student learning, exercise self-determination in instructional decisions, and recognize their impact on the school community. Also, this finding supports the study of Yorulmaz et al. (2018) whose findings showed that faculty exhibited a high level of psychological empowerment. Teachers are structurally and psychologically empowered by organizations that support them and create a facilitative atmosphere, which has an impact on their autonomy.

In addition, faculty shown a high level of psychological empowerment. Teachers are particularly able to complete the jobs that have been delegated to them. In addition to having a direct say in decisions that affect the institution, teachers also have a greater say in decision-making and are granted autonomy, freedom, and the chance to select how they carry out their duties (Lipae, 2025). Likewise, teachers reported a high level of psychological empowerment. Teachers find their work meaningful, feel confident in their skills, and experience autonomy in carrying out their responsibilities. Also, teachers perceive themselves as having a strong influence and control over departmental outcomes (Altinkurt, 2016).

Status of Organizational Commitment Among Private Tertiary Faculty

The status of organizational commitment of private tertiary faculty in Region XI was found to be descriptively high. This means that the organizational commitment of private tertiary faculty is oftentimes evident in the workplace. This finding implies that faculty tend to remain loyal and dedicated to their institutions. Their emotional attachment and sense of moral obligation drive them to perform their duties passionately and uphold the school's goals and values. At the same time, their awareness of the benefits and opportunities tied to staying reinforces stability and reduces turnover within the organization. The status of organizational commitment was assessed across different dimensions such as affective, continuance, and normative commitment.

This finding corroborates the inquiry of Roncesvalles and Gaerlan (2021), which study displayed a high level of teachers' organizational commitment. Despite being under a lot of strain, the teachers wanted to stay with their organization since they were happy and dedicated to their work. Teachers that are committed to their organizations will not be impacted by any amount of work-related stress. Instead, their work habits and devotion to the company show how happy and satisfied they are. This finding reinforces the investigation of Getahun et al. (2016) who expressed that teachers have high status of organizational commitment. Teachers feel obliged to remain in their current school as they have a strong emotional bond with their coworkers and supervisor.

Moreover, educators have high status of organizational commitment. The organizational commitment provides institutions with vitality, competitiveness, and the capacity to face challenges head-on. Additionally, employees usually go above and beyond what is expected of them since they feel like they belong and their goals coincide with the company's (Guhao, 2019).

Significance of the Difference on the Level of Organizational Commitment when Analyzed by Employment Status

When analyzed according to the respondents' employment status, there is no significant difference in the status of organizational commitment among private tertiary faculty in region XI. This implies that their attachment to the institution is not solely dependent on tenure. Faculty members, regardless of status, still develop emotional attachment to their school, recognize the costs and disruptions of leaving, and feel a moral sense of obligation to stay.

This result aligns with the findings of Palta (2019) who revealed that teachers' perceptions about organizational commitment do not vary in accordance employment status. Employees that are committed to the institution are thought to put in more effort and sacrifice to help the organization reach its objectives.

However, this result contradicts the study by Parveen (2015) who reported that compared to full time teachers, part time teachers have a greater degree of organizational commitment. Teachers are willing to put in a lot of work on behalf of the institution. Thus, it is beneficial to instill in employees a solid desire to remain with the institution.

Significance of the Difference on the Level of Organizational Commitment when Analyzed by Subject Taught

When analyzed according to the respondents' subject taught, there is no significant difference in the status of organizational commitment among private tertiary faculty in region XI. This implies that faculty members across disciplines demonstrate similar status of affective, continuance, and normative commitment. This suggests that their emotional association to the organization, recognition of the costs of leaving, and sense of moral obligation to stay are not influenced by the specific subjects they handle.

This result reinforces the study of Joolideh and Yeshodhara (2009) that subject taught by educators did not have influence on their organizational commitment. This means that whether a teacher teaches any other subject, it does not really affect the high status of organizational commitment of Iranian and Indian teachers. Likewise, Li et al. (2023) cited that subject taught does not significantly influence organizational commitment among teachers. Teachers have the same level of organizational commitment regardless of the subject they handled.

On the other hand, this result contradicts the study of Gökyer, (2018) which emphasized that there is a significant difference in organizational commitment after analyzed according to subject taught. Teachers' sense of participation and commitment to institutional progress are influenced by the discipline; they perceive a stronger connection between their field and the school's developmental objectives.

Significance of the Difference on the Level of Organizational Commitment when Analyzed by School Location

When analyzed according to the respondents' school location, there is no significant difference in the status of organizational commitment of private tertiary faculty in Region XI. This implies that faculty members demonstrate comparable status of affective, continuance, and normative commitment irrespective of either they are teaching in urban or rural settings. This suggests that their emotional attachment, apparent necessity of staying, and sense of moral obligation to remain with the institution are not determined by geographical location.

This result contradicts the findings of Erdogan and Cavli (2019) who revealed that there is significant difference on the organizational commitment of teachers when grouped based on the location of the school. Teachers in urban areas tend to demonstrate higher levels of organizational commitment compared to those in rural settings. Generally, many educators aspire to work in urban schools, where they have greater access to resources, professional growth opportunities, and support systems. Consequently, teachers assigned to rural areas may express a desire to transfer to urban institutions, which can affect their level of attachment and engagement. Likewise, Srinivasam and Selvi (2016) affirmed that there is a significant difference between urban and rural educators. It was shown that teachers in urban areas are more dedicated than those in rural areas.

Similarly, educators in urban areas tend to exhibit a higher level of organizational commitment compared to those in rural settings. This is attributed to the greater availability of professional development opportunities, stronger institutional support, and more collaborative environments in urban schools, which enhance teachers' sense of belonging and engagement with their institutions (Wang et al., 2017). However, educators teaching in the rural areas were more committed than the teachers working in the urban areas. It is concluded that rural teachers are more committed than their urban counterparts. This can be the result of less job options for teachers in rural areas unlike to those in urban zones. As a result, teachers in rural areas exhibit devotion and

dedication to the company (Shah & Mahmood, 2021).

Significance of the Difference on the Level of Organizational Commitment when Analyzed by Type of School

When analyzed according to the respondents' type of school, there is no significant difference in the status of organizational commitment of private tertiary faculty in region XI. This implies that faculty members demonstrate similar status of affective, continuance, and normative commitment regardless of whether they are teaching in sectarian or non-sectarian institutions. This suggests that teachers' emotional attachment, awareness of the consequences of departure, and sense of moral duty to remain are unaffected by the sort of school in which they are employed.

The result is consistent with the analysis of Para (2017), which found organizational commitment of teachers in the district of Srinagar have no significant difference based on school type. Faculty members show consistent status of affective, continuance, and normative commitment regardless of whether they are teaching in universities or colleges, or in sectarian or non-sectarian schools.

However, this result contradicts the study of Bell-Ellis (2015), which accentuated that compared to those at the secular university, faculty at the faith-based university were far more dedicated to their organization. Teachers teaching in faith-based university also had a better attitude at work.

Significance of the Difference on the Level of Organizational Commitment when Analyzed by Length of Service

When analyzed according to the respondents' length of service, there is significant difference in the status of organizational commitment of private tertiary faculty in region XI. This implies that faculty members' affective, continuance, and normative commitment vary depending on how long they have been with the institution. This suggests that the longer teachers remain in service, the stronger their attachment to the organization becomes, as they develop deeper emotional ties, recognize greater costs of leaving, and feel an increased sense of obligation to stay. Conversely, those with shorter tenure may exhibit lower commitment since they have had less time to build strong connections or invest in the institution.

This result corroborates the study of Parveen (2015) who cited that employees who have worked for the establishment for a relatively extended amount of time tend to feel a stronger sense of organizational commitment. While employees with less work experience are less committed to their organizations, those with greater work experience also show a higher status of organizational commitment. Also, this finding supports the study of Tiangco (2018) whose study confirmed that there is significant difference on the organizational commitment in terms of service length of the private school teachers. Organizational commitment increases with the length of service among teachers. This suggests that the longer teachers remain in the institution, the more they find meaning in

their work, identify with the organization's goals, and willingly contribute to its well-being.

Similarly, this finding affirms the investigation of Önder et al. (2019) whose study described that the status of organizational commitment varied significantly with seniority. Teachers with more than 31 years of seniority showed a more positive organizational commitment than those with 11–20 years. To put it another way, the organizational commitment levels of instructors varied depending on their degree of seniority. Likewise, a study of Tadesse (2019) found a moderate negative relationship between years of service and both normative and continuance commitment, implying that as teachers remain longer in the profession, their sense of obligation to stay and their perception of the costs of leaving tend to decrease.

Also, longer-serving teachers showed greater dedication to their organizations. The reason for this could be that teachers with a lot of seniority have been with their schools for a long time due to emotional attachment, and they do not have the stamina to start again at another school. Additionally, senior and older professors typically hold onto the status and respect they have earned at their current institution (Cobanoglu, 2020). Additionally, there is a significant difference in the overall organizational commitment of faculty when it comes to service years. Respondents with more than 10 years of service have a higher level of dedication than those with fewer than or equal to five years of service. It states that the organizational commitment increases with the number of service years (Agrawal & Jain, 2020).

Standpoints of Private Tertiary Faculty On their Organizational Commitment: A Priori Themes

Standpoints on Affective Commitment

Most participants recognized receiving recognition and trust from leadership and supporting professional growth opportunities. Additionally, they appreciate student success and gratitude and find purpose in teaching as vocation. Further, they acknowledge experiencing positive institutional culture and valuing small gestures of appreciation.

The result supports the findings of Tindowen et al. (2020) who emphasized that teachers demonstrate affective organizational commitment as they identify strongly with their institution and develop an emotional attachment that makes them view the school as a family. This sense of belonging fosters their willingness to remain in the organization for much of their careers. Another key factor behind this attachment is the school culture, which shapes their positive experiences, strengthens their loyalty, and ultimately influences their decision to stay. Furthermore, the finding is consistent with the inquiry of Getahun et al. (2016) that teacher exhibited affective commitment. Teachers stay in the organization as supervisors foster fulfilling work environment, and encouraging good work experiences as a way teachers grow with the organization.

Affective commitment refers to the emotional attachment employees feel towards

the organization. Teachers exhibit greater affective commitment thus having feelings of warmth, admiration, and loyalty towards the organization, stemming from their good ideas and interactions, and possess a strong desire to remain inside the organization (Sezen-Gultekin et al., 2021). In the same manner, teachers are proud of their self-selected decision to become educators. Additionally, they think that the teaching profession's values are crucial. Teachers already accept the principles of the teaching profession and identify with it. Highly devoted teachers are happy instructing their students and are able to do their assignments with passion and delight (Batugal & Tindowen, 2019).

Standpoints on Continuance Commitment

Participants expressed varied forms of continuance commitment, citing reliance on financial incentives, scholarships, and career advancement opportunities. Many also stay in their institutions to preserve benefits, maintain tenure and experience, and fulfill their responsibilities as family breadwinners.

The result is compatible with the study of Batugal and Tindowen (2019) which emphasized that given their commitment to their jobs, teachers find it extremely difficult to leave their organizations for a variety of reasons. In addition to the expense of quitting the company, they may not have many options for finding other employment. Consequently, educators remain with the institution due to their inability to depart and their apprehension over the financial and social repercussions of such a decision.

This finding also matches the research of Erdogan and Cavli (2019) which explained that educators' commitment to the school is strengthened and team performance is enhanced when they go above and beyond the call of duty. Additionally, by putting in more effort, they are able to receive internal and external rewards, such as pay and benefits. Additionally, elements like well-thought-out lesson plans, a positive work atmosphere, equitable pay, and additional chances for teacher involvement boost their organizational commitment.

Additionally, employees may be more entitled to obtain both psychological rewards in association with the institution and extrinsic rewards, such as compensation and benefits, depending on their level of organizational commitment. It is commonly believed that organizational commitment lowers abandoning behaviors, like unpunctuality and turnover (Getahun, et al., 2019). Similar to this, the majority of teachers have a commitment to stay with their institutions because they consider the risks and expenses of quitting, and they may do so if offered better options (Bashir & Gani, 2022).

Standpoints on Normative Commitment

Participants expressed diverse views on their normative commitment, staying in their institutions out of alignment with institutional values, gratitude for opportunities, and a sense of duty to students' success. They also demonstrated loyalty through collegial responsibility, adherence to cultural expectations, and emulation of their leaders' commitment.

This study is congruent to the study of Cogaltay (2015) which noted that some faculty members do not merely obey the regulations because they're required to. They truly held the rules and values of the institution as their own. They consider themselves as a vital component of the company and feel like they really belong. Since it originates from the heart rather than under duress, this is the strongest level of commitment. Similarly, the study of Barton (2016) emphasized that teachers with normative commitment are motivated to work for an organization due to a favorable perception of it and alignment with its mission and objectives. These committed faculty members actively assist the company's operations and elect to remain on staff voluntarily. Committed and passionate educators advance the organization's vision, and reduce costs, and cultivate positive cultures.

Moreover, educators often persist within the company because to robust cultural and familial values, which contribute to normative organizational commitment (Batugal & Tindowen, 2019). Likewise, faculty members are also currently happy in their teaching positions and have not indicated any desire to leave. Because they are happy with their professions, they find their schoolwork to be manageable and are willing to use a variety of instructional modalities and materials to fulfil the requirements of their students (Lantican, 2021).

Organizational Commitment of Private Tertiary Faculty in the Context of Employment Status

Faculty members, regardless of their employment status, shared similar perspectives on organizational commitment. Both full-time and part-time faculty expressed a deep sense of belonging, dedication to their institution's goals, and emotional attachment to their work. Their commitment appeared to stem not from the nature of their employment but from shared professional values, meaningful relationships, and a collective desire to contribute to student success and institutional growth.

This finding confirms the study of Tiangco (2018) whose study cited that teachers regardless of employment status have the same standpoints on organizational commitment. Irrespective of their job status, they all feel committed, emotionally invested in the company, and personally accountable for its success. Both teachers also have faith in the organization's beliefs, which is why they adopt them as their own and go above and beyond to uphold those values and aims.

Similarly, Jaron et al. (2015) found that there are no noticeable difference faculty in how full-time and part-time teachers experience organizational commitment. From a qualitative perspective, this suggests that loyalty and dedication to the institution transcend employment status. Participants shared that fairness and equal treatment within the organization foster a shared sense of belonging, allowing both full-time and part-time teachers to feel equally valued and connected to the institution's goals.

Organizational Commitment of Private Tertiary Faculty in the Context of Subject Taught

Faculty members across different subject areas expressed similar experiences of organizational commitment. Regardless of their academic discipline or field of specialization, teachers described a shared sense of dedication, loyalty, and connection to their institution. Their commitment appeared to stem from common professional values, passion for teaching, and collective responsibility for student learning, rather than from the specific subjects they teach.

Similarly, the inquiry of Joolideh and Yeshodhara (2009) noted that the subject taught did not appear to shape how teachers experienced or expressed their sense of organizational commitment. Teachers from various disciplines shared comparable experiences of dedication and attachment to their schools, emphasizing that their commitment stemmed from shared professional values and a collective sense of purpose rather than from their specific subject areas. This suggests that, regardless of what they teach, teachers cultivate a consistent sense of loyalty and connection to their institution rooted in their passion for education and commitment to student success.

Organizational Commitment of Private Tertiary Faculty in the Context of School Location

Faculty members shared comparable experiences of organizational commitment regardless of their school's location. Whether teaching in urban or rural settings, they expressed similar feelings of loyalty, dedication, and attachment to their institutions. Teachers described their commitment as rooted in shared professional values, supportive relationships, and a common desire to contribute to student success, rather than being influenced by geographical context.

However, this finding contradicts the study of Gökyer (2018) who reported that teachers from urban and rural areas expressed different experiences on organizational commitment. Teachers in urban areas described experiencing a deeper sense of connection with their colleagues and a stronger involvement in their institution's growth compared to those in small towns. Participants from urban schools shared that access to resources, professional collaboration, and supportive leadership nurtured their sense of belonging and commitment. In contrast, some teachers in rural areas reflected on challenges such as limited resources and professional isolation, which at times affected their engagement in institutional development.

Also, this finding contrasts with the study of Altinay (2024), which highlighted notable differences in the experiences of teachers in rural and urban schools. Rural schools are often characterized by open and friendly communication, a close-knit and cooperative atmosphere, and an environment that fosters mutual support and collaboration among teachers. The smaller and less crowded setting allows for stronger interpersonal relationships and a greater sense of community, which can enhance teachers' organizational commitment. In contrast, communication in urban schools tends to be more formal, limited, and at times impersonal due to larger school populations and busier environments.

Organizational Commitment of Private Tertiary Faculty in the Context of Type of School

Faculty members shared similar experiences of organizational commitment regardless of the type of private tertiary institution where they served. Whether teaching in universities or colleges, they described comparable feelings of dedication, loyalty, and connection to their schools. Their commitment appeared to stem from shared professional values, meaningful relationships, and a collective desire to contribute to institutional goals, rather than from differences in school type.

This result supports the study of Diamante (2012) which explored the factors influencing organizational commitment among faculty members in private educational institutions encompassing both sectarian and nonsectarian schools. Teachers across these institutional types shared similar experiences of commitment, expressing strong loyalty, dedication, and identification with their respective schools. Regardless of school type, teachers conveyed a comparable depth of attachment and responsibility toward their institutions.

However, this finding contrasts with the study of Bell-Ellis (2015), which revealed differing experiences of organizational commitment between faculty in faith-based and nonsectarian universities. Teachers in faith-based institutions described a deeper sense of purpose and stronger emotional connection to their organization, often rooted in shared values, faith, and a mission-driven work environment compared to teachers in nonsectarian institutions. These educators expressed that their beliefs aligned closely with the institution's vision, fostering greater dedication and positive attitudes toward their work.

Organizational Commitment of Private Tertiary Faculty in the Context of Length of Service

From a qualitative perspective, variations in organizational commitment were observed based on length of service. Long-serving faculty expressed deeper loyalty and attachment developed through years of engagement and familiarity with the institution, while newer teachers showed strong enthusiasm and a desire to contribute. Despite these differences in expression, both groups demonstrated a consistently high level of commitment to their institution and its goals.

A parallel understanding can be traced in the study of Brodish (2024) which emphasized that teachers, regardless of their tenure, consistently associated their organizational commitment and perception of school culture with the quality of relationships they maintained with both leadership and colleagues. In her study, teachers described how supportive and appreciative leadership fostered collegial cooperation and positive interactions among staff. Some participants shared that acknowledgment from leaders created a harmonious and encouraging work atmosphere, while others noted competitive tendencies. Despite these differing experiences, all participants highlighted that the strength of interpersonal relationships within the school community played a crucial role in shaping their sense of belonging and organizational commitment.

Also, early-career teachers expressed commitment through enthusiasm and openness to growth, though some admitted to exploring other opportunities for better benefits and career advancement as they were still adapting to the institution's culture. Meanwhile long-serving educators described a deeper, more enduring attachment rooted in familiarity, loyalty, and shared experiences within the organization. While their expressions of commitment varied, both groups reflected a genuine dedication to their institution and its mission (Clarence & George, 2018).

Data Integration of Quantitative and Qualitative Results

The results revealed a merging confirmation, as the qualitative narratives of teachers reinforced and substantiated the quantitative findings, showing consistency and coherence between both strands of data. This systematic process led to a more holistic and meaningful understanding of teachers' organizational commitment. This confirmation is reflected in the high status of organizational commitment, indicating that teachers select to remain in their institution because of their developed robust emotional attachment to it, feel a sense of responsibility to remain, and recognize the practical benefits of remaining. Specifically, all three indicators identified in the quantitative phase were reflected as *a priori* themes in the qualitative phase: affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment.

Furthermore, the finding corroborates the research of Tindowen et al. (2020), which highlighted that teachers exhibit a high level of organizational commitment because they form an emotional bond with their school and identify with it, viewing it as a family. They are more likely to stay with the company for the majority of their careers when they feel like they belong. Further, the finding aligns with the study of Erdogan and Cavli (2019) which accentuated that work-related factors, prospects for advancement, teammates, pay, and supervision all contributed to increased organizational commitment. Furthermore, Bashier and Gani (2022) revealed that there is a reciprocal interaction between the universities and the professors. Teachers react more resolutely when they have high organizational commitment because they believe they are an essential component of the organization. They are more driven and committed to fulfilling organizational objectives.

Moreover, teachers are more likely to be enthusiastic about maintaining their membership and remaining on staff when they sense a sincere and moral commitment to being a part of their schools and accept the school as a part of them. Moreover, it will lessen the likelihood of unanticipated and unexpected events occurring within the organizations. One significant factor in ensuring the smooth operation of the school and its continuation is the reduction in unforeseen circumstances brought about by organizational commitment (Nartgün & Menep, 2010). Likewise, employee commitment is increased when they are honest and open about their work, obligations, and duties. An employee's commitment to a firm is a strong motivator since it guarantees that they will strive towards the company's goals while simultaneously accomplishing their own (Hafiz, 2017).

In addition, in the area of significant differences in organizational commitment, it was found that there is no significant difference in the overall organizational commitment of private tertiary faculty in terms of employment status, subject taught, school location, and type of school (see Tables 4, 5, 6, and 7), while a significant difference in terms of years of service is found (see Table 8). Nonetheless, the qualitative results supported these quantitative findings, as they aligned with the *a priori* themes: Affective, continuance, and normative commitment. Therefore, the nature of data integration is characterized as merging-confirmation.

Also, this finding is comparable to the results of various studies on organizational commitment, such as that Palta (2019), which reported no significant differences in organizational commitment of teachers according to employment status. Also, Joolideh and Yeshodhara (2009) found no significant difference in organizational commitment of teachers in terms of subject taught. Likewise, in the study of Para (2017), no significant difference was found in organizational commitment of teachers when analyzed according to school location. Moreover, Diamante (2012) found no significant difference on the status of organizational commitment of professors when analyzed according to school type. On the other hand, Parveen (2015) revealed that there is significant difference in the organizational commitment of professors when analyzed according to years of service.

Conclusions

The status of authentic leadership among the tertiary faculty was rated very high. This means that authentic leadership among faculty is always manifested. This indicates that they view their leaders as genuine, transparent, and trustworthy in their actions and decisions. In addition, results showed that faculty also possess a very high status of psychological empowerment which means that psychological empowerment among faculty is always observed. This indicates that they feel self-assured, valued, and proficient of making meaningful contributions to their institution. Moreover, teachers were found to have a high status of organizational commitment. This means that organizational commitment of teachers is oftentimes evident in the workplace. This indicates that they are emotionally attached, morally obligated, and practically inclined to remain in their organization.

Additionally, no significant difference was found in the status of organizational commitment of respondents when analyzed by employment status, subject taught, school type, and school location. However, a significant difference was seen in the organizational commitment of participants when analyzed by length of service.

Further, the standpoints of private tertiary faculty on their organizational commitment are reflected in the themes of affective, normative, and continuance commitment. Faculty members expressed strong emotional feeling and identification with their institutions, a sense of moral duty and loyalty to remain, and recognition that leaving would disrupt both their lives.

Furthermore, the findings indicated that faculty experiences significantly differed according to their length of service, with those possessing less than five years in the institution articulating opinions that differed with those of their more experienced colleagues. This indicates that faculty below 5 years length of service may have distinct perspectives, needs, and levels of adjustment compared to faculty with more than 5 years length of service highlighting the importance of targeted support and development initiatives during the initial years of service.

Moreover, the merging confirmation of quantitative and qualitative findings reveals that private tertiary faculty in Region XI demonstrate a very high level of affective commitment and high levels of continuance and normative commitment. This convergence confirms that their organizational commitment is influenced more by emotional attachment, moral obligation, and the perceived cost of leaving than by demographic or institutional factors, with length of service identified as the only variable showing a significant difference.

Likewise, the intervention plan designed to enhance continuance and normative commitment highlights the interplay between faculty recognized costs of quitting, and their sense of moral obligation to remain with the organization. By addressing both economic and ethical dimensions of organizational commitment, the plan establishes a holistic framework for cultivating a more stable and committed workforce.

Recommendations

The status of authentic leadership and psychological empowerment is very high. It is recommended that the Human Resource Department institutionalize authentic leadership through leadership development, succession planning, and values formation programs, integrating transparency and ethical practices into recruitment, promotion, and evaluation. To enhance psychological empowerment, academic leaders may provide teachers with greater autonomy, participatory decision-making, and professional growth opportunities through involvement in curriculum design, research, and leadership roles. The status of organizational commitment is high. To maintain and improve this commendable level of devotion, it is advisable that the administration may persist in fortifying initiatives that foster shared leadership, professional development, and psychological empowerment. Acknowledging and appreciating academic contributions, promoting transparent communication, and offering ongoing career advancement possibilities may sustain this elevated level of organizational commitment and guarantee long-term institutional stability.

Further, given that no significant differences were found in organizational commitment when respondents were grouped according to employment status, subject taught, school type, and school location, it is recommended that institutions maintain consistent policies and practices that promote commitment across all teacher groups. However, since a significant difference was observed when analyzed by length of service, school administrators and the Human Resource Department are encouraged to design targeted retention and support programs for teachers at different career stages.

Furthermore, since faculty members' organizational commitment is reflected in affective, normative, and continuance commitment, it is recommended that school administrators and the Human Resource Department may implement strategies that holistically address these areas. Strengthening engagement and professional growth can enhance affective commitment, reinforcing loyalty and shared values can build affective and normative commitment, and ensuring competitive compensation and career stability can sustain continuance commitment.

In addition, since the status of continuance commitment and normative commitment is high, it is recommended that school administrators, in collaboration with the Human Resource Personnel, and academic leaders such as deans and department heads, may adopt and implement the intervention plan developed in this study. This plan provides targeted initiatives that address the normative and continuance dimensions of commitment, serving as a practical guide for sustaining and further enhancing faculty loyalty and dedication beyond demographic or institutional influences.

Lastly, future researchers may investigate more deeply the significant difference in organizational commitment when grouped according to length of service by conducting studies across larger and more diverse populations. They may also employ qualitative or mixed-method approaches to capture the lived experiences of instructors at different stages of their professions.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers are fully committed to maintaining the utmost ethical standards during the entirety of this investigation. The complete research was submitted for review and approval by the University of the Immaculate Conception – Research Ethics Committee (UIC-REC) to guarantee adherence to established ethical guidelines. In addition, the researchers provided the participants with the ICF to sign, which attests to their voluntary participation in the inquiry. The complete procedure, the aim, potential hazards, and any discomforts were elucidated to the volunteers. It was communicated to them that their responses would be kept confidential and that pseudonyms will be used in order to conceal their identities. The researchers also communicated the rights of participants to discontinue their involvement in the research at any moment and to refuse to answer any questions that were proposed to them. Furthermore, the researcher of this study is a licensed professional and an experienced educator with over six years of experience in teaching in tertiary education, currently pursuing a Doctor of Philosophy in Education major in Educational Leadership. Throughout the conduct of this inquiry, the researcher worked in close teamwork with her adviser, Dr. Avee Joy B. Dayaganon, who held a Ph.D. in Educational Leadership, served as the Vice-President for Academics at the University of the Immaculate Conception, and was a seasoned PAASCU Accreditor and CHED RQAT member in Region XI. Together with the guidance of panel members who are experts in educational leadership and research methodology, their critical feedback ensured the scholarly integrity of the research process and outcomes. Also, the researcher was trained in this field of study and passed a comprehensive exam. To summarize, she conducted the study due to the prevalent concerns of organizational

commitment among private tertiary faculty in the Philippines, and she was confident that her adviser would be willing to support her in completing it.

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